

A STUDY OF SELF CONTROL OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Cite This Article: Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar, "A Study of Self Control of Higher Secondary Students", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Page Number 22-26, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016.

Abstract:

The purpose of the paper is to determine the self control of higher secondary students. The sample consists of 300 higher secondary students for the study. The samples were selected by using simple random sample from vellore district, Tamilnadu. The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, SD, "t" test and 'F' test. Self Control Scale (SCS) was used for measuring the self control as part of decision making process which was developed by Arun Kumar Singh, Ph.D., Alpana Sen Gupta, Ph.D. The results reveal that the higher secondary students irrespective of their gender, locality of institution, type of institution, medium of instruction, religion, community, parental education, birth order and type of family have average level of self control and further it shows that there is insignificant difference between the gender, locality of institution, type of institution, medium of instruction, religion, community, parental education, birth order and type of family have average level of self control towards higher secondary students.

Introduction:

The prime function of education is to draw out the potentialities of the child and develop them to meet the challenging situations in life. Proper education will make the child understand the society and adjust with the social environment. School education can become better through quality education that can be nurtured through teacher education. Teacher education is providing quality education to the prospective teachers in educational philosophy, educational psychology and educational technology apart from the techniques of teaching. The quality of education depends upon the quality of teachers. Thus the role of the teachers is very important in making the nation. If the teachers are versatile, intellectually enlightened, morally strong, emotionally balanced, socially and culturally advanced, then the nation will have enlightened and excellent citizens.

Self Control:

The self control is one of the leading notions. Self control contributes to prevent undesirable behaviours without the teacher's interference. Self-control, self-regulation, self-orientation, self-management, internal control, self investigation and inner discipline are very similar notions. Self control is also an expected behaviour from contemporary people. Borba (2001) defines moral intelligence as the seven features for a student to behave appropriately and to resist the pressure that damage his/ her character (Charles, 2008). These seven basic features are empathy, conscience, self-control, respect, courtesy, tolerance and honesty. According to Borba (2001) the first three forms are the core of moral. Self Control Capacity is another reliable predictor of achievement (e.g., Duckworth 2009 & Seligman, 2005) Self-control is defined as the process of overriding or modifying one's own inner responses including impulses, emotions, thoughts or behavioural tendencies (Baumeister, Heatherton & Tice, 1994; Tangney, Baumeister & Boone, 2004). People higher in dispositional Self control capacity are more successful in this regard (Tangney et al., 2004). This means, individuals higher in self control capacity are supposed to be better at retraining their impulses (e.g. withstanding fattening snacks), in controlling their emotional expression (e.g. hiding anger), in shielding their attention from distraction and in sticking with unpleasant but important tasks. The last mentioned instances point out that a high self-control capacity is an advantage in the learning process. Behavioural Self control consists of at least two behavioural responses connected by a functional relationship in that one response controls the other (Cooper, Heron & Heward, 1987). There must be the target behaviour that the child or those around the child, identifies to change and the self control behaviour that is used to change the target behaviour (Belfiore & Hornyak, 1998; Cooper et al., 1997). In operant terms, there must be a controlled and a controlling behavioural response. Example of behavioural self control in everyday life is numerous.

Statement of the Problem: The problem chosen for the study may be stated as "A Study of self control of higher secondary students.

Sample of the Study: The sample consists of 300 higher secondary students for the study. The samples were selected by using simple random from vellore district, Tamilnadu.

Method: Descriptive survey method was used to conduct study of self control of higher secondary students.

Statistical Techniques Used: The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, SD, "t" test and 'F' test to accept or reject hypotheses

Operational Definitions of Key Term Used: Self Control is one of the dimensions of the personality which refers to ability to inhibit the expression of impulses by a way of resistance to temptation, delay of gratification and freedom from self centeredness in the classroom, family and social and peer group situations.

Tool Used in the Present Study: Self Control Scale (SCS) was used for measuring the self control as part of decision making process which was developed by Arun Kumar Singh, Ph.D., Alpana Sen Gupta, Ph.D.

Description of the Tool: The maximum possible score is 30. The subjects place a tick-mark on the cell below either “yes” or “No” for scoring each correct answer is to assigned a score of 1 and incorrect answer a score of zero. There are two types of items, positive items that are endorsed by the pupils or subjects as “yes” and all negative items that are endorsed by the subjects as “No” are given a score of +1. A score of zero is awarded to all other answers. Thus high score on the test indicates high self control and low score indicates low self control on the part of the subjects.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of self Control of higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their gender.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their locality of institution.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their type of institution.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their medium of instruction.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their religion.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their community.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their parental qualification.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their birth order.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their type of family.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ The Self Control of higher secondary students belonging to the following sub-samples is high.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their locality of institution.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their type of institution.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their medium of instruction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their religion.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their community.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their parental qualification.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their birth order.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in mean scores of the self control of higher secondary students with respect to their type of family.

Descriptive Analysis - Self Control Score of Higher Secondary Students:

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis For Self Control Scores of Higher Secondary Students

Demographic Variable	Sub-Sample	N	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	162	19.19	6.50
	Female	138	19.21	6.13
Locality of Institution	Rural	140	19.30	6.38
	Urban	160	19.12	6.29
Type of Institution	Government	147	19.34	6.00
	Aided	57	19.43	6.31
	Private	96	18.85	6.85
Medium of Instruction	English	136	18.98	6.52
	Tamil	164	19.39	6.17

Religion	Hindu	152	19.21	6.00
	Christian	96	18.91	6.91
	Muslim	52	19.71	6.20
Community	FC	35	19.68	5.97
	OBC	148	19.22	6.64
	MBC	56	18.96	6.38
	SC	61	19.11	5.79
Parental Education	Illiterate	98	19.30	6.32
	School Education	106	18.66	6.32
	College Education	96	19.70	6.35
Birth order	1 st	122	18.97	6.039
	2 nd	95	19.31	6.034
	3 rd	83	19.42	7.09
Type of Family	Nuclear	161	19.39	6.48
	Joint	139	18.98	6.15

In this study, based on normal curve of higher secondary students secured scores in between 12.88 to 25.52 (-1σ to $+1\sigma$) are classified as having average level of self control. In the table 1, shows the self control mean and standard deviation values. The calculated mean values are less than 429.85 and more than 252.73. Therefore, it is found that the higher secondary students irrespective of their gender, locality of institution, type of institution, medium of instruction, religion, community, parental education, birth order and type of family have average level of self control.

Differential Analysis for Self Control Scores of Higher Secondary Students:

Table 2: 't' value of Male and Female in their Self Control

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Remark
Male	162	19.19	6.50	0.027	N.S
Female	138	19.21	6.13		

It is evident from the table 2, the calculated 't' value is 0.027 which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found between Male and Female higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control.

Table 3: 't' value of Rural and Urban in their Self Control

Locality of Institution	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Remark
Rural	140	19.30	6.38	0.23	N.S
Urban	160	19.12	6.29		

It is evident from the table 3, the calculated 't' value is 0.23 which is not significant at 0.05 level hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Rural and Urban institution with respect to their Self Control.

Table 4: 'F' Value of Type of Institution with respect to Self Control

Type of Institution	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	DF	F Value	Remark
Between the groups	17.88	8.94	2	0.222	N.S
Within groups	11955.30	40.25	297		
Total	11973.18		299		

It is evident from the table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 0.222 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of type of institution with respect to their Self Control.

Table 5: 't' value of English and Tamil in their Self Control

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Remark
English	136	18.98	6.52	0.551	N.S
Tamil	164	19.39	6.17		

It is evident from the table 5, the calculated 't' value is 0.551 which is not significant at 0.05 level hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control.

Table 6: 'F' Value of Religion with respect to Self Control

Religion	Sum of squares	Mean square	DF	F Value	Remark
Between the groups	21.35	10.67	2	0.265	N.S
Within groups	11951.84	40.24	297		
Total	11973.18		299		

It is evident from the table 6, the calculated 'F' value is 0.265 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of Religion with respect to their Self Control.

Table 7: 'F' Value of Community with respect to Self Control

Community	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	DF	F Value	Remark
Between the groups	11.87	3.95	3	0.098	N.S
Within groups	11961.31	40.41	296		
Total	11973.18		299		

It is evident from the table 7, the calculated 'F' value is 0.098 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of community with respect to their Self Control.

Table 8: 'F' Value of Parental Education with respect to Self Control

Parental Education	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	DF	F Value	Remark
Between the groups	56.76	28.382	2	0.707	N.S
Within groups	11916.42	40.123	297		
Total	11973.18		299		

It is evident from the table 8, the calculated 'F' value is 0.707 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of Parental Education with respect to their Self Control.

Table 9: 'F' Value of Birth Order with respect to Self Control

Residence of Students	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	DF	F Value	Remark
Between the groups	11.49	5.74	2	0.143	N.S
Within groups	11961.69	40.27	297		
Total	11973.187		299		

It is evident from the table 9, the calculated 'F' value is 0.143 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of birth order with respect to their Self Control.

Table 10: 't' value of Nuclear and Joint in their Self Control

Type of Family	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Remark
Nuclear	161	19.39	6.48	0.562	N.S
Joint	139	18.98	6.15		

It is evident from the table 10, the calculated 't' value is 0.562 which is not significant at 0.05 level hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between nuclear and joint family with respect to their Self Control.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that the higher secondary students irrespective of their gender, locality of institution, type of institution, medium of instruction, religion, community, parental education, birth order and type of family have average level of self control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Male and Female higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control on their Gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control on their locality of institution.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among the sub-samples of Type of institution with respect to their Self Control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between English and Tamil of higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control on their Medium of instruction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among the sub-samples of Religion with respect to their Self Control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among the sub-samples of Community with respect to their Self Control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among the sub-samples of Parental Education with respect to their Self Control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among the sub-samples of Birth Order with respect to their Self Control.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint of higher secondary students with respect to their Self Control on their Type of Family.

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